

THE IMPACT OF IT TRAINING ON EMPLOYEE PERFORMANCE IN SMALL ORGANIZATION - OMAN

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Abstract: As known that the IT training and management of human resources very important for any organization, the measure of success of any organization is measured by the extent to which pre-established goals are achieved, which depend mainly on the workforce. Therefore, in order to improve the organization's performance, organizations must focus on information technology and invest in this field. However, we do not see many organizations working to invest in the field of information technology, because they do not put it among their priorities, and some of these organizations still feel that training employees to engage in this field is unnecessary. These organizations are working to reduce the budget allocated to IT to reduce annual expenses or to save some revenues. A stratified sampling method was used and 60 employees from a community of 300 were targeted through a self-administered questionnaire. The aim of this questionnaire is to find out the effect of training employees on information technology and motivating them to develop their skills, as well as knowing job satisfaction in small organizations. This study concluded that training on information technology has increased the performance of employees and also had a positive impact on the performance of the organization.

Keywords: Employees performance, IT training, Training, Small organization.

I. INTRODUCTION

Employee performance is an important part of production. According to some researchers, human resources are the driving force behind any business activity (Brayfield & Crockett, 1955). Therefore, the task of the manager is to retain employee's for the sake of the survival and continuity of the institutions (Rosita et al., 2020). However, competition in the field of work for productive and skilled employees is a great task, so preserving productive employees requires sacrifices from the employer (Gouin-Bonenfant, 2022). Productive employees have future aspirations, plans and visions for growth, but if they do not find the opportunity to achieve this in the current place, they will look for opportunities in other institutions (Eisenberger & Stinglhamber, 2011) (Olsson, 2007). The inability to retain a skilled employee leads to a shortage in production, which has a significant impact on the organization economically (Humphries et al., 2018) (Bao & Nizam, 2015)). Performance is one of the strategies used by human resource managers through which to attract and retain productive

employees as well as facilitate them in order to improve performance and comply with the organization's labor laws and regulatory legislation (Tabassi & Bakar, 2009). There were many studies on IT training and its impact on employee performance (Shahzadi et al., 2014). Studies have shown that IT training is one of the most important elements in raising and maintaining employee performance (Bao & Nizam, 2015). This research is an attempt to study the impact of IT training on employee performance and will provide an example of organizations that consider IT training.

In our research, we will focus on the most important practices used in small first-class enterprises to raise the level of performance of their employees. Therefore, the results expected in this study will help in understanding the impact of IT training on the performance of employees in institutions and provide recommendations that help human resource managers to improve IT training methods (Pihl & Peterson, 1995) (Maduka & Okafor, 2014).

II. PROBLEM STATEMENT

Through literature-based empirical studies, it is clear that many institutions are working to reduce budgets because one of their primary goals is to increase revenues. Certainly, this policy leads to the emigration of many competencies in the institution. Thus, this has a negative impact on the performance of the institution and also an increase in costs. The emigration of such competencies leads the company to search for a replacement to replace him, and it is difficult to find a replacement with the same efficiency and the same cost, since rehiring a new person in the organization costs more than retaining an existing employee (Haustein, 2014). According to Saranani (2015), there has been a noticeable increase in anxiety among employees in small organizations, both in the private and public sectors, as they attempt to navigate an increasingly complex work environment. This pressure to adapt and improve employee performance is compounded by the need to reduce IT training budgets, which can have a negative effect on workers' skills and experience. However, this situation may not only affect these employees' performance but also have more general impacts. In the modern work environment, employees need to continuously develop their skills, knowledge, and experience to adapt to the constant changes. As a consequence, hiring new employees can be expensive, leading to employee motivation and job satisfaction issues that may result in a high job turnover rate. (Naqvi & Khan, 2013) (Nda & Fard, 2013). As a result, the hiring process becomes more expensive, leading to a decrease in net profits in the long run (Kim & Ployhart, 2014). Therefore, this study aims to fill the current research gap by examining how IT training affects the performance of employees in a smaller organization.

Research Objective

With reference to the aforementioned problem that was encountered during IT training for employee performance, here several challenges and opportunities that may arise for employees, in addition to factors that improve employee performance at work, have been clarified and discovered by researchers. Here are some of the main objectives as follows:

- 1- To address the process of addressing current problems in training IT and employee performance.
- 2- To recognize the relationship between IT training and employee performance.
- 3- To complete the process of examining the impact of IT training on employee performance.

Research questions

1. What is the impact of IT training on employee performance?
2. What is recognize the relationship between IT training and employee performance.?
3. How to address the current problems in IT training and employee performance?

Significance of this study

The study of IT training is one of the most important topics that must be dealt with on an ongoing basis. However, this study is important to identify effective standards for IT training, which directly affect employee performance. Therefore, the study will help small government institutions to develop a IT training strategy through results that will indicate the effectiveness of the types of IT training related to employee performance. It will also provide an assessment of the appropriate type of IT training for each employee, and the extent to which the employees benefit from such IT training.

The importance of this study lies in knowing the impact of IT training on workers in institutions that work in the field of information technology IT training for small organizations and its role in improving the efficiency and performance of the employee, obtaining the highest experience, increasing job satisfaction and making the institution rise to become more successful. It also reduces errors, as errors occur on a regular basis. It is important for employees who lack the skills and abilities required to complete the work. Therefore, IT training makes the employee's error rate low and makes him more efficient in his work. This study also aims to improve the level of employee performance, in addition to gaining experience.

III. RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

The method of defining the subject of the research, the method of defining the study community, collecting data, and defining the research sample was carried out within regular stages and based on scientific methods, as shown in the following figure

Design of the study: The study involved using various research designs to collect and analyze data in line with the research goals. The literature outlines different methods of counting and gathering information and measuring it appropriately. The research included both quantitative and qualitative designs, with a focus on qualitative research during the survey phase. This approach was deemed suitable as it did not interfere with the factors, variables, and results being studied.

Data sources and collection methods: This study used raw data that was compiled by containing several open and closed questions. It allowed the respondents in order to answer the questions in their free time and also helped to develop the accuracy of the information.

Target Group Sample size and sampling Technique: The duty of definition and its rule, that Individuals are defined as a group of organisms or people, a certain number of whom are chosen to take an appropriate sample. This is in context process of the discussion in the study being conducted at the present time, and this is considered stressful on the part of the study, because there is a large number of residents, and this is due to a number of reasons, including, for example, the lack of time, costs, accessibility, and more. Where some of individuals and the people that were targeted for the study were reduced to 18 employees consisting of 5 employees from the upper management and also 10 employees from the middle management and 3 employees from the basic level, which is the junior level in small organization. Based on these categories, it is a representative sample.

Validity of the research Instrument: Validity indicates the limit reached by the search tool is used to measure what it means to be measured. Where the validity of the tool was determined, that is through do a questionnaire in this case, it was used to collect data, which is by making sure that all the questions in the questionnaire are compatible with the research questions that are comprehensive for the study and are also comprehensive to its objectives. And although the validity and how valid was the questionnaire verified by putting the experimental by testing some of the respondents, this is only to test and measure their understanding and interpretation of the questions, and this allows us to make sure that such questions carry some intent and that the inquiries and / or the two comments whose effect is represented in These respondents have been used to adjust these questionnaires (Kothari, 2004).

How Reliable is the Research tool? Reliability of a reliable research tool: It is the extent to which it reveals the performance of the research used in collecting information and data in a study of conformity with the objective. To document the guarantee of the tool, ten HRM professionals conduct the questionnaires in a scientific research manner. Therefore, to clarify this questionnaire, it was chosen to be experimental and therefore revised.

Research hypothesis

This research will address the following hypotheses:

H1. There is a significant impact of the effectiveness of IT training on the performance of employees in small government institutions.

H2. IT Training positively affects the performance of employees in small government institutions.

Data analyzing

The methodology that was worked on and applied in the study follows an approach that has been used by several published works in order to validate and evaluate the model as well as the hypotheses. Several procedures are applied, which start with measurement evaluation, followed by structural evaluation. This data was collected and collected through a structured questionnaire. In addition, data analysis by SPSS-21 was used. It includes descriptive statistics, reliability analysis, regression and correlation analysis, pie chart analysis, and percentage analysis. Here also the demographic portions of this questionnaire were analyzed using percentage analysis and pie chart. On this basis of the questionnaire, sections and parts related to the variables are analyzed through the use of descriptive correlation and regression. Tables and graphs are provided where applicable with explanations given. As Creswell explains, pilot testing for research purposes helps researchers provide an idea of whether respondents have the ability to complete a questionnaire and how well they understand the questions. As the most important thing is that the suitability of the definitions used and the research methodology can be ascertained. As the experimental study aimed at is the extent of the impact of IT training on the questions that are related to the performance of employees. It is also very important to evaluate the questionnaire questions and to be clear and understandable to all groups.

Table 1: Reliability Statistics

Cronbach's Alpha	N of Items
.634	18

Demographic analysis

The demographic details collected by the questionnaire for the respondents are analyzed using percentage analysis and are represented schematically using pie charts. Eight elements were included in the demographic analysis (age, gender, marital status, department, rank, educational qualification, income level, experience the job).

Gender Distribution

The target audience was the employees who work in the Elite The target audience was the employees who work in the Elite department in small enterprises, in order to determine the impact of IT training on them. The appropriate sample was used, which resulted in 158 correct answers, with females making up 6.86% and males 13.4% of the total correct answers.

This is the gender and refers to it in our questionnaire. This resulted in 136 responses (response rate 6.86%), 21 males (response rate 13.4%). As shown in Table 2 below. The average number of elective fitness was 178.0 out of 4..

Table 2: Gender Distribution

		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	Female	136	86.6	86.6	86.6
	Male	21	13.4	13.4	100.0
	Total	157	100.0	100.0	

Figure 2: Gender responses

Age analysis

The resulting age distribution stratification was as follows: (a) Group 1 (18-25.5 years) represented 71.3%. (b) Group 2 (35.5-26) represents 17.8%. (C) Group 3 (45.5-36) represents 7.6%. (d) Group 4 (55.5-46) representing 3.2%. The dominant group is group a after that group b, while the least dominant group is group d.

Table 3: Age analysis

		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	18-25,5	112	71.3	71.3	71.3
	26-35,5	28	17.8	17.8	89.2
	36-45,5	12	7.6	7.6	96.8
	46-55,5	5	3.2	3.2	100.0
	Total	157	100.0	100.0	

Figure 3: Age analysis**Highest Educational Qualification**

These are the qualifications we refer to in the questionnaire.

The results that appeared for 26 (valid high school or below) (16.6% response rate), 40 (Diploma) (25.5% response rate), 85 (Bachelor's Degree) (54.1% response rate), 3 (Master's Degree) (1.9% response rate), 3 (PhD or above) (1.9% response rate), As shown in Table 4 below, and the average number of elective fitness was 2.471.

Table 4: Qualification

		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	High School or below	26	16.6	16.6	16.6
	Diploma	40	25.5	25.5	42.0
	Bachelor's Degree	85	54.1	54.1	96.2
	Master's Degree	3	1.9	1.9	98.1
	PhD. or above	3	1.9	1.9	100.0
	Total	157	100.0	100.0	

Figure 4: Qualification Pie chart.

Numbers of years of study

This sub-characteristic in the work experience relates to the ability of the model component to interact with other components within the work experience, and the interoperability in the work experience results in 37 responses (first year) (response rate 23.6%), 21 (second year) responses (13.4% response rate), 28 (third year) responses (17.8% response rate), and 71 (fourth year) answers (45.2% response rate). The largest number of research participants obtained (first year) and (fourth year), as shown in Table 5 below. The average number of optional interoperability is 2.847 out of 4.

Table 5: Numbers of years of study

		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	First year	37	23.6	23.6	23.6
	Second year	21	13.4	13.4	36.9
	Third year	28	17.8	17.8	54.8
	Forth year	71	45.2	45.2	100.0
	Total	157	100.0	100.0	

Figure 5: Numbers of years of study Pie chart.**work experience**

This is the work experience we refer to in our questionnaire. Results that emerged from 68 (one year) responses (43.3% response rate), 22 (two years) responses (14.0%), and 21 (three years) responses (13.4 response rate), And 28 (four years) (17.8% response rate), and 18 (five years) (11.5% response rate), as shown in Table 6 below. The average number of elective fitness was 377.0.

Table 6: work experience

		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	One years	68	43.3	43.3	43.3
	Two years	22	14.0	14.0	57.3
	Three years	21	13.4	13.4	70.7
	Four years	28	17.8	17.8	88.5
	Five years	18	11.5	11.5	100.0
	Total	157	100.0	100.0	

Figure 6: work experience Pie chart

Income level

Here we are talking about the income level, which is indicated in our survey. The results showed 72 (350-200 OMR) responses (response rate 45.9%), 24 (550-500 OMR), 26 (750-600 OMR), 19 (950-800 OMR), 16 (100 riyals or more), as shown in Table 7 below. And the average was 2.255.

Table 7: Income level

		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	OR200 – OR350	72	45.9	45.9	45.9
	OR500 – OR550	24	15.3	15.3	61.1
	OR600 – OR750	26	16.6	16.6	77.7
	OR800 –OR950	19	12.1	12.1	89.8
	OR1,000 and above	16	10.2	10.2	100.0
Total		157	100.0	100.0	

Figure 7: Income level Pie chart

(Main research question)

MRQ1: Have you received any form of IT training since joining the organization?

This is Q1 that he referred to in our survey. Where the result was obtained 93 answers (response rate 59.2%), 64 (no) answers (response rate 40.8%), as shown in Table 8 below. The mean number of elective fit was 221.0.

Table 8: IT training since joining the organization

		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	Yes	93	59.2	59.2	59.2
	No	64	40.8	40.8	100.0
	Total	157	100.0	100.0	

Figure 8: IT training since joining the organization Pie chart.

MRQ2: How long have you undergone IT training in small organizations?

This is Q2 and it refers to it in our survey. This resulted in 26 responses (every two years) (with a response rate of 16.6%), 24 responses (every six months) (with a response rate of 15.3%), and 22 responses (once a year) (with a response rate of 14.0%), and 3 responses (quarterly) (with a response rate of 1.9%), As shown in Table 9 below. The mean number of elective fit was 562.0.

Table 9: undergone IT training in small organizations

		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	Every two years	26	16.6	16.6	16.6
	Every six months	24	15.3	15.3	31.8
	Once a year	22	14.0	14.0	45.9
	Quarterly	3	1.9	1.9	47.8
	No specific schedule	82	52.2	52.2	100.0
	Total	157	100.0	100.0	

Figure 9: undergone IT training in small organizations Pie chart.

MRQ3: What are the ways of facilitation in IT training that the employee receives?

This is Q3 and it refers to it in our survey. Result in 62 (Lecture) responses (39.5% response rate), 16 (Demonstrations) responses (10.2% response rate), 27 (Discussions) responses (17.2% response rate), and 29 (presentation) responses (18.5% response rate), 23 (Seminar) responses (14.6% response rate) as shown in Table 10 below. The mean number of elective fit was 406.0.

Table 10: the ways of facilitation in IT training that the employee receives

		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	Lecture	62	39.5	39.5	39.5
	Demonstrations	16	10.2	10.2	49.7
	Discussions	27	17.2	17.2	66.9
	Presentation	29	18.5	18.5	85.4
	Seminar	23	14.6	14.6	100.0
	Total	157	100.0	100.0	

Figure 10: the ways of facilitation in IT training that the employee receives Pie chart.

MRQ4: Is IT training experience gained while delivering training within the small organization?

We were referring to this Q4 question in our survey. The outcome resulted in 13 (strongly disagree) answers (8.3% response rate), 11 (disagree) answers (7.0% response rate), 47 (Neutral) answers (29.9% response rate), 70 (Agree) answers (44.6%). 16 (Strongly Agree) answers (10.2% response rate), as shown in Table 11 The mean number of elective fit was 536.0.

Table 11: IT training experience gained while delivering training

		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	Strongly Disagree	13	8.3	8.3	8.3
	Disagree	11	7.0	7.0	15.3
	Neutral	47	29.9	29.9	45.2
	Agree	70	44.6	44.6	89.8
	Strongly Agree	16	10.2	10.2	100.0
	Total	157	100.0	100.0	

Figure 11: IT training experience gained while delivering training Pie chart.

MRQ5: The purpose of IT training for employees to gain experience?

This is Q5 and it refers to it in our survey. The result is 9 responses (strongly disagree) (5.7% response rate), 8 responses (disagree) (5.1 % Response Rate), 24 Response (neutral) (15.3% percent Response Rate), 70 Response (Agree) (44.6 % Response Rate), 46 Response (Strongly Agree) (29.3 % Response Rate) , as shown in Table 12 below. The mean number of elective fitness was 607.0.

Table 12: The purpose of IT training for employees to gain experience

		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	Strongly Disagree	9	5.7	5.7	5.7
	Disagree	8	5.1	5.1	10.8
	Neutral	24	15.3	15.3	26.1
	Agree	70	44.6	44.6	70.7
	Strongly Agree	46	29.3	29.3	100.0
	Total	157	100.0	100.0	

Figure 12: The purpose of IT training for employees to gain experience Pie chart.

MRQ6: Competencies and skills pre-requisite for employee performance can be achieved through IT training?

This is Q6 and it refers to it in our survey. The result is 9 responses (strongly disagree) (5.7% response rate), 8 responses (disagree) (5.1 % Response Rate), 24 Response (neutral) (15.3 percent Response Rate), 70 Response (Agree) (44.6 % Response Rate), 46 Response (Strongly Agree) (29.3 % Response Rate), as shown in Table 13 below. The mean number of elective fitness was 570.0.

Table 13: Competencies and skills pre-requisite for employee performance

	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	Strongly Disagree	13	8.3	8.3
	Disagree	6	3.8	12.1
	Neutral	37	23.6	35.7
	Agree	71	45.2	80.9
	Strongly Agree	30	19.1	100.0
	Total	157	100.0	100.0

Figure 13: Competencies and skills pre-requisite for employee performance Pie chart.

MRQ7: Employees get some benefits when they participate in a special IT training program in the organizations where they work?

This is Q7 and it refers to it in our survey. The result is 9 responses (strongly disagree) (5.7% response rate), 8 responses (disagree) (5.1 % Response Rate), 33 Response (neutral) (21.0 percent Response Rate), 79 Response (Agree) (50.3% Response Rate), 28 Response (Strongly Agree) (17.8% Response Rate) , as shown in Table 14 below. The mean number of elective fitness was 580.0.

Table 14: Employees get some benefits when they participate in a special IT training program

		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	Strongly Disagree	9	5.7	5.7	5.7
	Disagree	8	5.1	5.1	10.8
	Neutral	33	21.0	21.0	31.8
	Agree	79	50.3	50.3	82.2
	Strongly Agree	28	17.8	17.8	100.0
	Total	157	100.0	100.0	

Figure 14: Employees get some benefits when they participate in a special IT training program Pie chart.

MRQ8: There may be challenges related to IT training and development within the organization?

This is Q8 and it refers to it in our survey. The result is 10 responses (strongly disagree) (6.4% response rate), 7 responses (disagree) (4.5 % Response Rate), 33 Response (neutral) (21.0% percent Response Rate), 85 Response (Agree) (54.1% Response Rate), 22 Response (Strongly Agree) (14.0% Response Rate), as shown in Table 15 below. The mean number of elective fitness was 580.0.

Table 15: challenges related to IT training and development within the organization

		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	Strongly Disagree	10	6.4	6.4	6.4
	Disagree	7	4.5	4.5	10.8
	Neutral	33	21.0	21.0	31.8
	Agree	85	54.1	54.1	86.0
	Strongly Agree	22	14.0	14.0	100.0
	Total	157	100.0	100.0	

Figure 15: challenges related to IT training and development within the organization Pie chart.

MRQ 1: To what extent does IT training affect job performance?

This is Q2 and it refers to it in our survey. The result is 13 responses (have no positive effect) (8.3% response rate), 22 responses (slight positive effect) (14.0 % Response Rate), 42 Response (moderate positive effect) (26.8% percent Response Rate), 50 Response (a significant positive effect) (31.8% Response Rate), 30 Response (a very significant positive effect) (19.1% Response Rate), as shown in Table 16 below. The mean number of elective fitness was 533.0.

Table 16: IT training affect job performance

		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	have no positive effect	13	8.3	8.3	8.3
	slight positive effect	22	14.0	14.0	22.3
	moderate positive effect	42	26.8	26.8	49.0
	a significant positive effect	50	31.8	31.8	80.9
	a very significant positive effect	30	19.1	19.1	100.0
	Total	157	100.0	100.0	

Figure 16: IT training affect job performance Pie chart.

MRQ2: How did the IT training affect your job performance?

This is Q2 and it refers to it in our survey. The result is 7 responses (have no positive effect) (4.5% response rate), 22 responses (slight positive effect) (14.0 % Response Rate), 33 Response (moderate positive effect) (32.5% percent Response Rate), 44 Response (a significant positive effect) (28.0% Response Rate), 33 Response (a very significant positive effect) (21.0% Response Rate), as shown in Table 17 below. The mean number of elective fitness was 545.0.

Table 17: the IT training affect your job performance

		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	have no positive effect	7	4.5	4.5	4.5
	slight positive effect	22	14.0	14.0	18.5
	moderate positive effect	51	32.5	32.5	51.0
	a significant positive effect	44	28.0	28.0	79.0
	a very significant positive effect	33	21.0	21.0	100.0
	Total	157	100.0	100.0	

Figure 17: the IT training affect your job performance Pie chart.

MRQ3: Does the IT training affect the performance of your duties and responsibilities within the organization?

This is Q3 and it refers to it in our survey. The result is 13 responses (strongly disagree) (8.3% response rate), 12 responses (disagree) (7.6 % Response Rate), 43 Response (neutral) (27.4% percent Response Rate), 64 Response (Agree) (40.8% Response Rate), 25 Response (Strongly Agree) (15.9% Response Rate) , as shown in Table 4.19 below. The mean number of elective fitness was 547.0.

Table 18: the IT training affect the performance of your duties and responsibilities

		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	Strongly Disagree	13	8.3	8.3	8.3
	Disagree	12	7.6	7.6	15.9
	Neutral	43	27.4	27.4	43.3
	Agree	64	40.8	40.8	84.1
	Strongly Agree	25	15.9	15.9	100.0
	Total	157	100.0	100.0	

Figure 18: the IT training affect the performance of your duties and responsibilities Pie chart.

IV. CONCLUSION

The importance of IT training in the world of organizations has been widely studied. There are large collections of theoretical and empirical literature, which provides evidence that has been studied before to support the direct or indirect link between IT training and employee performance and encouragement among employees with the positive repercussions that it indirectly classifies on performance. organizational. This is because the success and failure of any organization in achieving its objectives depends greatly on the IT training of its workforce. Therefore, there must be information with a lot within the organizations about the importance of investments in IT training the employee in order to improve his performance and thus the performance of the organization. enterprises through a self-questionnaire and using descriptive statistical methods to analyze the data.

However, it seems that some organizations (including small ones) are not aware of these concerns because they continue to put pressure on the IT training budget when their economic or financial conditions are not good, and these conditions hinder employees and reduce their performance, which reduces their performance. Motivation and increase job turnover and costs. Thus, hiring new employees reduces organizational profitability. Thus, this project examined the effect of IT training on employee performance, employee motivation in the context of small enterprises, (including the initial issue) on the value of IT training on employee performance (productivity). In addition, the study is also highly involved in the general group to increase its knowledge in the literature on the associations between each of these variables that are found in the country. The study used stratified sampling methods to take a sample of 158 workers through a self-questionnaire and using descriptive statistical methods to analyze the data.

The results of the study showed that 30 respondents linked IT training to improving the performance of employees in small enterprises, while only 8.3% reported that IT training did not have a positive effect on the performance of employees in small enterprises, and their number was 13 people. In addition, the results also showed that about 19.9% and 13.9% of the respondents argued that IT training significantly affects significant and positive on employee performance and motivation.

In addition, the majority of respondents (21.0%) indicated that IT training increases the performance of workers in small enterprises. These experimental results are not consistent with those of other similar studies in the literature. But it has beneficial political implications for managers. In small organizations, organizations should allocate a dedicated budget solely for employee IT training based on identified skill gaps in order to hone the employees' skills, knowledge, abilities, and competence to enable them to adapt. With the business environment in the emergence of great financial innovation and financial development. Secondly, small organizations should develop IT training policies and continuous IT training programs in order to enhance employee performance and stimulate their job satisfaction. This will increase employee loyalty and commitment towards their organizations and also help organizations achieve strategic goals, vision and mission. Last but not least, small businesses must review and improve the working conditions of employees and give bonuses and benefits regularly in order to retain the talented workforce as these employees become more attractive to other organizations that have always wanted to build strong human resources to enhance competitive advantage against them. competitors.

H1. There is a significant impact of the effectiveness of IT training on the performance of employees in small government institutions.

H2. IT Training positively affects the performance of employees in small government institutions.

In these hypotheses operate on the effect of one variable on another variable. These variables are IT training and the other variable is employee performance. There are also questions affecting both groups.

Group 1: Questions RTMPIT2, RTMPIT3, IOIPTEP2, and IOIPTEP3 affect the first variable (IT training)

The second group: the effect of the question RTMPIT6, RTMPIT7 on the second variable (workers' performance).

discussion and conclusion In order to measure the validity of each item, the total percentage of the factor is up to 80% must be measured. The data collection tool is assumed to be valid when it is threshold value equal to or greater than 70% for each item and cumulative percentage. The value is equal to or greater than 80%. In addition, the average, mean and median, mode values must be equal to or greater than 2.00. We can note that the first construction of the questionnaire (RTMPIT2, RTMPIT5, IOIPTEP1, IOIPTEP2, IOIPTEP3) is close to agreement on the category (average, mean and median = 3.5592).

Since this value is between 80 and 89 range, it can be taken as an acceptable value. However, the values questions respectively from RTMPIT6 and RTMPIT7 (average, mean and median = 3.631). Close to agree also. In addition, the results that appeared up to (56) of RTPIT6, RTMPIT7, RTMPIT2, RTMPIT5, IOIPTEP2, IOIPTEP2, IOIPTEP3 are 57.4%, 65.6%, 75.75% and 18.5%. Accordingly, they can be considered acceptable results.

In this study, two hypotheses are explained in the theoretical framework section and the research credits may be higher than the results of the correlation coefficient according to Cronbach's alpha. It can also be seen that all hypotheses are supported, this helps that all paths are significant between all dependent and independent variables, where $H1 = 0.05 < 0.271$ describes the path between perceived ease of use and perceived usefulness, and also indicates that ease of use may enhance perceived usefulness in Hypothesis ($b = 0.386$, $p < 0.05$) The soft pathway shows perceived ease of use and behavioral intent, and perceived ease of use helps determine behavioral intent to use. Finally, we find that this study indicates that RTMPIT, IOIPTEP positively affect the behavioral intention of users as easy and beneficial.

Hypothesis Testing Result

Table 19: hypothesis testing result

Hypotheses	Path	Path coefficient	P-value	Remarks
H1	RTMPIT-IOIPTEP	0.271	0.001	Supported
H2	IOIPTEP-RTMPIT	0.386	0.001	Supported

On the basis of testing the samples collected for analysis, this resulted in the effect of all variables. It also shows a positive impact of IT training, but it is not considered significant on employee performance. In addition, it is possible that, in some analyses, the improvement of employee performance in organizations will decrease, so the impact of such IT training on information technology will depend on the competency, through which the employee's efficiency will increase.

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